

SIROP

LOD-GEOSS

Open Energy Platform

Publication of FAIR Data and Metadata

Part 2:
Open Data Publication on
the Open Energy Platform

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Open Energy Family

Open Energy Family

Data Publication

- Parse or copy as CSV
- Use existing data models
- Make database conform
- Follow naming conventions

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Technology					PV - renewable power - st	
2	year		2015	2020	2030	2040	2050
3	est.		ctrl	ctrl	ctrl	ctrl	ctrl
4	Est. par.						
5	Energy/technical data						
6	Generating capacity for one unit [MW_e]		0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
7	Forced outage []		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
8	Planned outage [weeks per year]		0	0	0	0	0
9	Technical lifetime [years]		30	35	40	40	40
10	Construction time [years]		0	0	0	0	0
11	Space requirement [1000 m2/MW_e]		6.67	5.37	4.78	4.49	4.23
12	Regulation ability						
13	Primary regulation (of full load, per 30 seconds) []						
14	Secondary regulation (of full load, per minute) []						
15	Financial data						
16	Nominal investment (*total) [2020-MEUR/MW_e]		1.43	0.87	0.57	0.46	0.41
17	Nominal investment (*total, per DC) [2020-MEUR/MW_e]		1.3	0.79	0.51	0.42	0.38
18	Nominal investment (grid connection) [2020-MEUR/MW_e]			0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03
19	Nominal investment (inverter) [2020-MEUR/MW_e]			0.17	0.11	0.09	0.08
20	Nominal investment (pv modules) [2020-MEUR/MW_e]		0.81	0.44	0.24	0.18	0.15
21	Nominal investment (installation) [2020-MEUR/MW_e]			0.13	0.11	0.09	0.09
22	Nominal investment (other, i.e. residual balance of plant) [2020-MEUR/MW_e]		0.61	0.09	0.07	0.06	0.06
23	Nominal investment (soft costs) [2020-MEUR/MW_e]						
24	Fixed O&M (*total) [2020-EUR/MW_e/y]		14300	10600	8900	8000	7500
25	Fixed O&M (land rent) [2020-EUR/MW_e/y]						
26	Technology-specific data						
27	Generating capacity for one unit (DC-value) [MW_e]		0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11
28	Space requirement (per DC) [1000m2/MW_e]		6.06	4.88	4.35	4.08	3.85

	id	model	scenario	region	type	year	generating_capacity	space_requirement	performance_ratio	full_load_hours_dc	full_load_hours
1	1	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_residential_2015	Europe	residential	2015	0.0063	6.06	0.79	934.72	981.46
2	2	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_residential_2020	Europe	residential	2020	0.0063	4.88	0.86	1010.33	1060.84
3	3	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_residential_2030	Europe	residential	2030	0.0063	4.35	0.95	1116.06	1171.86
4	4	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_residential_2040	Europe	residential	2040	0.0063	4.08	0.96	1127.81	1184.2
5	5	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_residential_2050	Europe	residential	2050	0.0063	3.85	0.97	1139.56	1196.53
6	10	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_industrial_2015	Europe	offshore	2015	0.11	6.06	0.81	950.59	1045.65
7	11	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_industrial_2020	Europe	offshore	2020	0.11	4.88	0.86	1010.33	1111.36
8	12	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_industrial_2030	Europe	offshore	2030	0.11	4.35	0.95	1116.06	1227.67
9	13	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_industrial_2040	Europe	offshore	2040	0.11	4.08	0.96	1127.81	1240.59
10	14	dea_technology_data_generation	pv_rooftop_industrial_2050	Europe	offshore	2050	0.11	3.85	0.97	1139.56	1253.51

Data Publication

- Create a good table title
- Columns and data types
- Finalise data structure

<https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/wizard/>

Data Publication

- Collect as much (meta) information as possible
- Create a simple JSON or use the **OEMetadata Builder**

<https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/oemetabuilder/>

Data Publication

- Search for existing OEO classes
- Open issues for missing concepts or contribute
- Focus on the most important values

Data Publication

- Ready for use
 - Access over URL, API or download as datapackage
 - Start the Open Peer Review on the OEP (under development)
- Register on the **Energy Databus**

„The opposite of **‘open’** isn’t **‘closed’**. The opposite of **‘open’** is **‘broken’**.“

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